

DataCite FAIRagro Metadata Analysis

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About

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Related Documents

- [Metadata Report performed by DataCite](#)

Background

The initial phase of this project is dedicated to establishing a comprehensive understanding of the persistent identifier (PID) landscape within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI).

This effort is led by PID4NFDI, a collaborative initiative involving DataCite, the Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung Göttingen (GWDG), the Helmholtz Open Science Office, and the Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB), Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology. The consortium works closely with experienced PID infrastructure users to leverage their insights and amplify the impact of PID adoption within NFDI workflows.

This report outlines the initial phase, which encompasses use-case analysis, requirements engineering, and concept development. These activities are designed not only to address immediate project needs, but also to ensure that the insights gained facilitate seamless integration and ongoing development in future project phases.

As part of our deliverables for the initialization phase work packages 1 and 2, this use-case analysis serves several key purposes:

- **Work Package 1 (WP1):** This encompasses deliverable **D1.1**, which focuses on exploring the landscape of PID practices across different NFDI services, and deliverable **D1.2**, which involves a requirements analysis of selected use cases to derive practical and relevant insights. These analyses set the stage for a broader understanding of how PIDs are implemented and managed across diverse research contexts within NFDI.
- **Work Package 2 (WP2):** Within WP2, deliverable **D2.1** aims to develop a conceptual framework for mapping selected use cases to existing PID services. The goal here is to ensure that our understanding of use cases

translates into actionable strategies for integrating PID services effectively across NFDI consortia.

Criteria for Use-Case Selection

The selection of use cases was a crucial step in ensuring a diverse and representative analysis. We established the following criteria for choosing which use cases to examine:

1. **Diversity in duration of operation and PID service providers:** We aimed to reflect a range of maturities, encompassing both well-established and newer initiatives. This variety helps us understand PID usage at different stages of project development and their engagement with different stakeholders (i.e., PID Providers).
2. **Disciplinary Breadth:** The use cases needed to span multiple disciplines to assess the adaptability and versatility of PID adoption across different scientific fields and sectors.
3. **Active Engagement:** The use cases had to demonstrate active contributions and engagement.

FAIRagro: A Comprehensive Use Case for PID Implementation

FAIRagro, a consortium within NFDI in Germany, has been selected as a key use case partner for PID4NFDI. FAIRagro's mission is to advance agrosystem research by fostering linkages across agronomy disciplines, scales, and methods through collaborative research data management. With 32 members representing diverse disciplines, FAIRagro¹ aims to develop an interoperable and scalable research data infrastructure that ensures all research outputs adhere to FAIR principles.

The consortium plans to activate and integrate infrastructure services towards a broader and FAIR-compliant research data landscape. This encompasses a range of repositories and infrastructures operated in the consortium. These vary in their degree of PID implementation, positioning FAIRagro as a valuable use case with the potential to serve as a best-practice model for other use cases within the NFDI consortia.

Selection Criteria and Insights from FAIRagro

The selection of the Genebank Information System (GBIS) at IPK Gatersleben as a representative use case within FAIRagro was guided by its alignment with key criteria that reflect its capacity to contribute meaningfully to PID4NFDI's goals:

1. **Maturity:** FAIRagro supports a variety of infrastructures, including the well-established GBIS at IPK Gatersleben. GBIS, in particular, demonstrates a high degree of readiness to integrate and test PIDs within its workflows, making it a robust candidate for piloting PID services for diverse entities.
2. **Data Connectivity and Diversity:** FAIRagro's emphasis on digital twins for material samples and associated metadata aligns seamlessly with PID4NFDI's objectives. GBIS has shown significant potential in leveraging digital twins to enhance data connectivity. In order to support a best level of material provenance and sample tracking the use of International Generic Sample

¹ Specka, X., Martini, D., Weiland, C., Arend, D., Asseng, S., Boehm, F., ... & Ewert, F. (2023). FAIRagro: Ein Konsortium in der Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) für Forschungsdaten in der Agrosystemforschung: Herausforderungen und Lösungsansätze für den Aufbau einer FAIRen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur. *Informatik Spektrum*, 46(1), 24-35.

Numbers (IGSNs) for material samples is on the roadmap to complement already used Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for research data. These efforts strengthen linkages across datasets, fostering interoperability and reinforcing FAIR principles².

3. **Disciplinary Breadth:** FAIRagro spans a broad spectrum of disciplines within agrosystem research, from conserving crop genetic diversity to advanced plant research and breeding. The inclusion of GBIS further exemplifies this breadth, as it operates at the intersection of conservation, research, and utilization of crop genetic diversity. This interdisciplinary approach underscores the relevance and adaptability of FAIRagro's objectives across diverse scientific contexts.
4. **Confirmed Engagement:** FAIRagro and GBIS have demonstrated sustained commitment through active participation in PID4NFDI initiatives. This includes contributions to a workshop in 2023³, a detailed quantitative survey⁴, an in-depth interviews conducted in 2024, and presentations on PID4NFDI use cases and services in February 2024⁵. Moreover, FAIRagro has committed to raising awareness of PID services among its members and testing these services within its portfolio of use cases, showcasing its proactive role in driving PID adoption and integration.

The Role of GBIS Within FAIRagro

GBIS plays a key role in FAIRagro's implementation and scaling of PID services. Managing data for over 151,000 accessions, GBIS provides a comprehensive repository that includes phenotypic observations, herbarium specimens, and associated imagery.

² Arend, D., Psaroudakis, D., Memon, J. A., Rey-Mazón, E., Schüler, D., Szymanski, J. J., ... & Lange, M. (2022). From data to knowledge—big data needs stewardship, a plant phenomics perspective. *The Plant Journal*, 111(2), 335–347.

³ Schrader, A. C., Arend, D., Bach, J., Elger, K., Göller, S., Hagemann-Wilholt, S., Krahl, R., Lange, M., Linke, D., Mayer, D., Mutschke, P., Reimer, L., Scheidgen, M., Selzer, M., & Wieder, P. (2023). Workshop on PIDs within NFDI (Version 1). Internal Workshop on PIDs within NFDI, Online. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7635905>

⁴ El-Gebali, S., Hagemann-Wilholt, S., Böhm, J., & Kahlert, T. (2024). D1.1 Landscape of PID practices within NFDI services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14277479>

⁵ Hagemann-Wilholt, S., Wieder, P., Martini, D., & Lange, M. (2024, February 20). PID4nfdi - Example Use Cases and Services for NFDI. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685209>

As part of its integration into FAIRagro, the medium-term aim is to establish digital twin services to uniquely identify and connect physical samples with their digital representations. Currently, DOIs are used to uniquely identify plant genetic resources. In order to connect physical samples with their digital representations, the next step could be to leverage International Generic Sample Numbers (IGSNs). This integration would enable the dynamic linking between physical and virtual components, fostering a FAIR-compliant ecosystem. This initiative is supported by the partnership between DataCite and IGSN, which facilitates the seamless registration of identifiers⁶.

Results

Our evaluation of FAIRagro – especially focussing on GBIS as a representative use case – was based on a comprehensive, multistep process that combined qualitative and quantitative analysis.

Metadata Analysis and Evaluation

To assess the metadata practices at GBIS, an analysis was conducted in October 2024. The evaluation focused on the quality and completeness of metadata submitted during DOI registration under the prefix 10.25642. The metadata, deposited under a CCO license, is managed by the Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research (IPK) Gatersleben.

Key Metrics:

- Total DOIs Registered: 209,872
- Strengths Identified: The use of ROR identifiers has increased significantly for research organizations, enhancing organizational visibility.

Challenges Identified:

- Metadata completeness for key fields such as licensing (available in only 312 DOIs) is attributed to the fact that these DOIs represent comprehensive datasets from eDAL-PGP platform, which inherently include license information. In contrast, the remaining ~200,000 entries, originating from GenBank, are accessions without license information.

⁶IGSN 2040 Vision to Execution <https://doi.org/10.5438/50t1-tq66>

- Funder information is lacking, limiting the ability to assess funding landscapes.
- Annotation inconsistencies, such as free-text resource type descriptions (“PGRFA material” vs. “PGRFA research material”), create barriers to standardization.
- Subject keywords suffer from inconsistent capitalization (e.g., “Wheat” vs. “wheat”) and different spellings (e.g., “ISA-Tab” vs. “ISATab”).
- Related identifiers, which are critical for tracking versions and connections between datasets, are present in only 3.7% of entries. This is largely due to the lack of an established workflow to update assigned DOIs after significant events, such as the publication of corresponding papers. For example, backlinks to the data are often missing, leaving the RelatedIdentifier attribute empty. Additionally, there are ongoing discussions about using the RelatedIdentifier attribute for GenBank GBIS DOIs to link accession history when updates are made to passport data, highlighting opportunities for improved integration and metadata enrichment.

These findings highlight areas for improvement in metadata practices, with actionable recommendations provided in the accompanying [Metadata Report by DataCite](#).

Survey Results: FAIRagro

Survey responses from different FAIRagro representatives offered valuable insights into the consortium’s infrastructure, challenges, and expectations regarding PID adoption. Key infrastructures supported by FAIRagro include:

Infrastructures and Services

FAIRagro oversees several key infrastructures that support the preservation, sharing, and publication of agrosystem research data, among them:

1. **e!DAL-PGP at IPK Gatersleben**⁷: This FAIR-compliant and open-source e!Dal software system supports sharing of data, archiving, preservation, and

⁷ <https://edal-pgp.ipk-gatersleben.de/>

publishing. Widely used by other consortia (e.g., ELIXIR), e!DAL-PGP is a recognized IPK repository mainly for plant research data.

2. **BonaRes Repository at ZALF**⁸: BonaRes Repository specializes in data publication and sharing, integrating with established data environments. While EOSC integration is unclear, it is well-embedded in existing research infrastructures.
3. **GBIS at IPK Gatersleben**⁹: Focused on archiving and preservation, GBIS is recognized internationally (e.g., ECPGR and FAO) and actively contributes to plant genetic resource research.

PID Integration and Metadata Practices

The three services have been integrating PID services for several years, with e!DAL-PGP registering its first DOIs in 2011, BonaRes in 2016, and GBIS in 2020. All services report mature adoption. IPK estimates between 101-1,000 DOIs to be registered annually, alongside active usage of ORCIDs (101-1,000 annually) and minimal use of ROR. In 2020, there was a bulk registration of ~200,000 DOIs from IPK (Figure 1a), and since 2021 (Figure 1b), there has been a consistent registration of between 101-1,000 DOIs annually through the three providers.

⁸ <https://maps.bonares.de/mapapps/resources/apps/bonares/index.html?lang=en>

⁹ <https://gbis.ipk-gatersleben.de>

Providers

- ipk.gbis:Genebank Information System of the IPK Gatersleben
- tib.bonares:BonaRes Leibniz-Zentrum für Agrarlandschaftsforschung (ZALF) e.V. Datenzentrum Agrarlandschaft
- tib.zalf:Leibniz-Zentrum für Agrarlandschaftsforschung (ZALF) e. V.

a)

Providers

- ipk.gbis:Genebank Information System of the IPK Gatersleben
- tib.bonares:BonaRes Leibniz-Zentrum für Agrarlandschaftsforschung (ZALF) e.V. Datenzentrum Agrarlandschaft
- tib.zalf:Leibniz-Zentrum für Agrarlandschaftsforschung (ZALF) e. V.

b)

Figure 1: DOI registrations per year from different providers a) up to year 2020 b) from 2021 onwards

Figure 2: a) Number of DOIs with ORCID IDs stratified by sub property from all 3 providers b) Number of DOIs with ROR IDs stratified by sub property from all 3 providers

Responses indicated high satisfaction with DataCite and ORCID services, reflecting trust in these established providers. ROR services, though also positive, rank slightly lower in satisfaction, possibly due to lower familiarity.

Key factors guiding membership and PID provider selection are strongly influenced by alignment with organizational goals, ease of integration into existing workflows, and overall awareness of PID ecosystems. Technical compatibility remains moderately influential, while cost considerations and community recommendations hold lesser sway.

Metadata Practices and Interoperability Efforts

According to survey results, members of the FAIRagro consortium actively participate in metadata working groups and employ standards such as OAI-PMH and REST APIs for interoperability. They also utilize DataCite's Metadata Schema to establish connections between PIDs, enabling effective linking of datasets, instruments, and other research entities.

The metadata standards used include DataCite, MCPD (Multi-Crop Passport Descriptors), and MIAPPE (Minimum Information About a Plant Phenotyping Experiment). Within FAIRagro, services also employ extensible self-defined metadata schemas, tailored to specific user needs while remaining compatible with applied standards. This extensibility highlights their adaptability and user-centered approach to metadata management.

FAIRagro operates in a complex data ecosystem where data varies significantly by type, format, and origin. Challenges include:

- The integration of diverse datasets generated by multiple stakeholders (e.g., private companies, research institutions).
- The need for interoperable identifiers to manage temporally and spatially resolved data, quantitative and qualitative traits, and agronomic records.

These challenges reinforce the importance of standardized metadata and the adoption of PIDs like DOIs and IGSNs.

Challenges and Support Needs

FAIRragro identified several challenges in sustainable PID implementation:

- **Staff and Resource Limitations:** Limited personnel and project-based funding models create obstacles for long-term PID management.
- **Integration Complexity:** Adapting PID services to legacy systems requires considerable effort, compounded by evolving standards.

To address these challenges, the respondents stated that targeted training and low-threshold information, potentially in German, on topics such as PIDs for specific research entities and data citation best practices would support their needs. They also express interest in joint outreach initiatives and collaborations across consortia.

Key Insights from the FAIRragro Survey Responses:

1. **Mature Infrastructure and Pre-NFDI Experience:**

FAIRragro's core data services (e!DAL-PGP¹⁰ and GBIS at IPK Gatersleben, BonaRes¹¹ at ZALF) pre-date the NFDI and are already established, widely used, and trusted. This indicates a strong operational foundation on which FAIRragro can build further PID integration and FAIR data practices.

2. **High Volume and Diversity of PID Usage:**

With between 101-1,000 DOIs estimated to be registered annually and anticipated active use of ORCID and ROR, FAIRragro demonstrates significant engagement with PID systems. Their satisfaction with PID providers like DataCite and ORCID is high, emphasizing an environment receptive to expanding PID integration.

3. **Strong Emphasis on Metadata and Interoperability:**

The analysed services within FAIRragro are proactive in adopting and refining metadata standards, participating in metadata working groups, and exploring

¹⁰ Arend, D., König, P., Junker, A., Scholz, U., & Lange, M. (2020). The on-premise data sharing infrastructure e! DAL: Foster FAIR data for faster data acquisition. *GigaScience*, 9(10), g1aa107.

¹¹ Hoffmann, C., Kühnert, T., Zoarder, M., Specka, X., Svoboda, N., Eberhardt, E., ... & Heinrich, U. (2019, January). The BonaRes Data Portal: FAIR access to Soil and Agricultural Research Data. In *Geophysical Research Abstracts* (Vol. 21).

digital twin and FAIR Digital Object concepts. They leverage multiple data exchange protocols (OAI-PMH, REST APIs) to ensure interoperability and facilitate the FAIR principles.

4. **Organizational Alignment and Awareness Drive Decisions:**

Decisions on PID membership and services are strongly influenced by how well solutions align with needs of each organization hosting the respective services, how easily they integrate into existing workflows, and the familiarity of service teams with PID tools. While cost and community recommendations matter, strategic and technical fit take priority.

5. **Training and Outreach Needs:**

The respondents value training to enhance PID understanding and usage. They have already participated in DataCite webinars and requested more targeted, low-threshold materials—potentially in German—and practical guidance on using PIDs for various research entities. Their outreach efforts focus on a broad audience, from researchers and librarians to IT professionals.

6. **Challenges in Sustainable PID Implementation:**

Limited staff resources, project-based funding models, and the complexity of integrating PID systems into legacy environments are ongoing hurdles. Evolving standards demand constant adaptation, reinforcing the need for shared best practices, community support, and stable governance structures for sustainable PID management.

7. **Eager for Cross-Consortium Collaboration:**

Respondents expect to work closely with PID4NFDI and other consortia on shared standards, co-developing policies, and coordinated helpdesk and training. They see these collaborations as integral to overcoming challenges, standardizing practices, and improving the overall FAIR ecosystem.

In summary, the insights on services within FAIRagro reflect an established, proactive consortium that values stability, strategic alignment, and interoperability. They seek support from PID4NFDI in establishing best practices, developing training resources, and fostering collaborations to streamline PID adoption and FAIR data management across diverse research communities.

Qualitative Insights: Interviews and Stakeholder Engagement

Overview of IPK's Role and Infrastructure

The **IPK Gatersleben** is a FAIRagro co-applicant, and furthermore, one of Europe's leading plant biodiversity research institutes, with a focus on plant genetic resources (PGR) and biodiversity preservation. The institute has developed an extensive infrastructure to manage research data, aligning with FAIR principles to support data reusability.

Key components of FAIRagro's infrastructure provided by IPK¹² include:

- **e!DAL-PGP**: A system for managing and publishing phenotypic and genotypic data, integrating DOIs via DataCite.
- **Genebank Information System (GBIS)**: Used for managing seed data and assigning DOIs to material accessions.
- **LIMSOPHY Laboratory Information Management Systems (LIMS)**: A federated system for data entry and management, ensuring data curation aligns with domain-specific requirements¹³.

PIDs at IPK

PID Integration and Challenges

IPK actively integrates multiple PIDs, including DOIs, IGSNs, ORCIDs, and RORs. However, challenges persist due to:

- The coexistence of legacy ID systems (e.g., accession numbers) with global standards like DOIs.
- Variability in adoption rates across user groups and institutions, reflecting differences in citation culture and technical familiarity.

IPK would benefit from expanding the use of **IGSNs** as part of a digital twin and FAIR digital object model for material samples. The perspective could be to mint millions of IGSNs to uniquely identify seeds and other entities in the research lifecycle.

¹² For an overview see: <https://fairagro.net/en/about-us/our-research-data-infrastructure/>

¹³ Ghaffar, M., Schüler, D., König, P., Arend, D., Junker, A., Scholz, U., & Lange, M. (2019). Programmatic access to FAIRified digital plant genetic resources. *Journal of Integrative Bioinformatics*, 16(4), 20190060.

Metadata Completeness and Quality

IPK faces metadata inconsistencies due to federated data management. Key issues include:

- Missing metadata fields such as funder information and licensing.
- Inconsistent naming conventions (e.g., localized terms for samples).
- Variability in metadata standards and schema adherence, requiring manual curation to ensure FAIR compliance.

Efforts to improve metadata quality include developing automated pipelines for metadata submission and implementing review processes for dataset publications.

Digital Twin and FAIR Digital Object Models

Through its collaboration with IPK, FAIRagro is exploring **Digital Twin (DT)** models to represent material samples as FAIR Digital Objects. This approach aims to:

- Establish provenance through unique identifiers for seeds, samples, field plots, and experimental data.
- Create a directed acyclic graph to connect donor materials to derived datasets and experimental results.
- Address scalability challenges, as digital twin models require robust systems capable of handling millions of identifiers.

Governance and Organizational Structure

Decentralized Governance

FAIRagro follows a decentralized governance model, granting autonomy to individual systems while maintaining alignment with consortium-wide guidelines. There is no centralized authority regulating PID usage, but minimal standards are enforced for metadata and identifier assignment.

Institutional Oversight

At IPK, IT and bioinformatics groups work collaboratively to ensure consistent governance of PIDs and data infrastructures. This structure supports:

- Oversight of proprietary and open-source systems.
- Technical integration and quality assurance for metadata and identifiers.

Training, Support, and Outreach

Training Needs and Formats

IPK has identified the need for:

- Consolidated training resources to address the oversupply of fragmented formats.
- Short, engaging materials (e.g., 5-minute videos) to improve accessibility for researchers.
- Domain-specific guidance on metadata curation and PID usage.

Current Training Practices

FAIRagro compiles training material¹⁴, provides a helpdesk¹⁵ and organizes events such as summer schools to educate researchers on plant phenotyping and metadata preparation. However, these are not regular or integrated into institutional onboarding processes.

Outreach Activities

Outreach efforts are limited to presentations and workshops. There is potential to expand awareness-building initiatives through targeted materials and broader engagement strategies.

Technical Challenges

Proprietary vs. Open Source Systems

IPK uses a mix of proprietary and open-source systems:

- Proprietary systems, like the LIMS, provide stability and long-term support but require careful management to avoid vendor lock-in.

¹⁴ <https://fairagro.net/en/how-to-learn-and-teach-rdm-a-collection/>

¹⁵ Schmidt, M., Rey-Mazón, E., Beyer, F., Singson, L. S., Vedder, L., Sahwan, W., & Svoboda, N. (2024, Juli 12). The FAIRagro Helpdesk – a direct link to our community's everyday needs. 1st FAIRagro Community Summit 2024, Berlin. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12731405>

- Open-source solutions, such as e!DAL-PGP, offer flexibility but depend on sustained development resources.

Data Interoperability

Interoperability remains a key challenge due to:

- Variations in ID systems and metadata schemas.
- The need for manual curation to align data from different sources with standards like MCPD (Multi-Crop Passport Descriptor) and MIAPPE.

FAIRagro's federated data entry model complicates efforts to ensure consistency, requiring technical and human oversight to achieve interoperability.

Cross-Consortium Collaboration

FAIRagro collaborates with other NFDI consortia to:

- Develop shared PID policies and metadata standards.
- Promote cross-domain integration of research data (e.g., linking weather, soil, and plant data).

Members of the consortium also participate in metadata working groups and contribute to global efforts to align identifier usage with international best practices.

Summary and Next Steps

The selected FAIRagro use case provides a comprehensive view of the challenges and opportunities associated with implementing and scaling PID services in complex, interdisciplinary research contexts. As a consortium with a mature and proactive approach to PID integration, the survey respondents and interview partners from FAIRagro have contributed valuable insights that align with and support the ongoing efforts of PID4NFDI.

These insights inform targeted **support activities by PID4NFDI**, focusing on the following areas:

Enhancing Metadata Quality and Standardization:

Offer targeted workshops and hands-on training to address critical metadata gaps. Emphasize standardizing resource type annotations and improving overall metadata consistency to ensure compliance with FAIR principles.

Strengthening Digital Twin Workflows:

Develop clear guidelines and workflows for minting IGSNs at scale, addressing the complexities of managing tens of thousands or even millions of sample-level identifiers.

Expanding Training and Outreach Initiatives:

Create accessible and engaging training materials, supporting multiple languages. Focus on specific PID-related topics to lower barriers to adoption and increase awareness across diverse research communities.

Promoting Cross-Consortium Collaboration and Knowledge Exchange:

Facilitate the sharing of experiences and best practices within and beyond NFDI consortia. Promote collaborative initiatives for PID implementation and offering incentives to encourage metadata curation.

Establishing Governance:

Support the formalization of PID governance guidelines across other NFDI consortia. Leverage collective NFDI resources and support to secure and define long-term management structures.

By addressing these areas, FAIRagro serves as a model for other consortia, advancing the overarching goals of PID4NFDI. These next steps lay the foundation for enhanced interoperability, improved data quality, and a more cohesive adoption of FAIR-aligned PID practices across research domains.